

Strategy and policy in preventing environmental pollution and degradation

Nur Adi Saputra and Gustan Pari
Forest Products Research and Development Center
E-mail: gustanp@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

Agricultural practices are relevant to productivity and environmental impact, a contradictory and an intriguing debate. A single process of agricultural has been identified to emit greenhouse gas (GHG). Even agricultural components, consisting of soil, water, rice varieties, organisms and interactions among components its self, contribute to climate change. Investigation of CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O emission levels needs to be strictly, especially on degraded agricultural land. Thus, soil processing, rice varieties, irrigation patterns, fertilization applications and pesticides are carried out as environmental mandates. The authors recommend the use of low-emission varieties, intermittent water management, agroforestry applications and biochar amendment from agriculture, estate and forest residue to minimize environmental impacts. Application biochar, compost and liquid smoke (3 in 1 technology) in agriculture and forest plantation its can be reduce CH₄, N₂O and CO₂ emission gas and increasing the yield of agriculture.

Keywords: agriculture, emission, greenhouse gas (GHG), biochar

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture faces economic interests, especially the development of manufacturing industry and its supporting infrastructure. Decreasing in land area, especially rice farm, occurs every year. Agricultural area decreased approximately 0.2% (2013) and 0.3% in 2014, equivalent 16 and 24 thousand ha of rice farm. Central Bureau of Statistics (BPS) data states that the rice farm in 2014 was 8.11 million hectares. Declining in area not in line to increasing in agricultural productivity. Indonesia rice production ranks third after China and India, both of which produce 55% of the global needs. In 2014, China produces more than 206 thousand tons, India production more than 157 thousand tons, while Indonesia produces about 70,000 tons. In fact, Indonesia productivity was 53.41 quintal ha⁻¹.

The government continues to increase agricultural production and productivity through intensification and extensification. Panca Usaha Tani Program: sustainable soil farming, irrigation, superior variety, fertilization and

eradication of pests, were representing agricultural land intensification. The implementation of agriculture extensification program carried out within framework of agrarian reform and social forestry (SF). The objective of agrarian reform was to grant ownership of converted forest to community, while the SF target was to increase people's access to forests by maintaining the primary mandate of the forest itself. The indicative allocation land of Agrarian Reform Object (TORA) according to Decree of the Minister of Environment and Forestry 180 / MENLHK / SETJEN / KUM.1 / 4/2017 was 4.85 million hectares. SF indicative area of approximately 13.46 million hectares (SK.22 / MENLHK / SETJEN / PLA.0 / 1/2017).

The exchange of information and experience in the implementation of intensification and extensification becomes crucial at this point, providing new perspectives and sustainable management mandates. Agriculture and climate have a sensitive relationship between the two. The function of agriculture as soil organic carbon (SOC) uptake contributes to stabilizing the earth's temperature rising below 2%. However, agricultural activity has the potential to increase the risk of climate change. Agricultural practices have the potential to release CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O emissions, all of which are an important part of GHG emissions, contributing around 60, 20 and 6%, respectively (Singla & Inubushi, 2013). Furthermore, agriculture, forestry and other land uses (AFOLU) are responsible for reducing GHG emissions. The target of AFOLU emission reduction was 10-12 GtCO₂eq .y⁻¹ to 0.6 GtCO₂eq .y⁻¹(Frank et al., 2017). Agriculture is responsible for lowering emission levels at the level of 0.008 GtCO₂eq .y⁻¹ (26% scenario) or 41% scenario of 0.011 GtCO₂eq .y⁻¹. The provisions are regulated in Presidential Regulation 61 Year 2011 on the National Action Plan for Green House Gas Emission Reduction (RAN GRK). The focus of this paper is to investigate agricultural practices, Panca Usaha Tani Program, through the environmental aspects approach.

DEFORESTATION AND DEGRADATION

The global meeting placed particular concern on deforestation and degradation. The summit of international recognition to deforestation and degradation occurred at the COP-13 in Bali. Parties agreed to accommodate deforestation and degradation through Reduction of Emissions from Deforestation and Degradation (REDD) mechanisms, and supplemented by sustainable forest management and increased carbon stock uptake. However, definition of "deforestation" and "degradation" itself has not been resolved in the REDD⁺ debate (Hosonuma et al., 2012). The initial approach was pinned on variabels that lead to forest deforestation and degradation. At least there were 5 drivers of deforestation (Hosonuma et al., 2012), namely: (1) commercial

agriculture, (2) subsistence, (3) mining, (4) infrastructure and (5) settlement expansion. While degradation triggers (Hosonuma et al., 2012) were: (1) logging, (2) uncontrolled fires, (3) livestock grazing and (4) firewood. The data on deforestation and degradation rates has not found accurately, given the dynamics of extent and forest cover occurring. These metadata becomes very important in carbon stock inventory. The calculation approach of carbon stock through emission factor (EF) and sequestration factor (SF) becomes logically accepted in such dynamic conditions. As a result, Indonesia has carbon stocks of 874.37 tonnes ha⁻¹, scattered in various forest cover (Rochmayanto et al., 2014), these finding has lower than the previous, 1 614.81 tonnes .ha⁻¹(Masripatin, Ginoga, et al., 2010), Table 1.

Table 1. Carbon stocks by forest in Indonesia

Natural forest	ton C .ha-1
Dipterokarpa	234.81
Protected	211.86
Fired forest (secunder)	31.4
Mangrove (secunder)	118.3
Cultivated (secunder)	210.45
Lowland (primery)	247.4
Highland (primery)	103.16
Lowland (secunder)	113.2
Highland (secunder)	39.48
Gambut	200
Fired peat	104.75
TOTAL	1614.81

AGRICULTURAL PRACTICES

Soil characteristics

Soil is an agro-fundamental productivity and affects all terrestrial life. This characteristic is attached to the nature of the soil and the reciprocal to the environment. A slight mismanagement leads to the land being vulnerable to degradation and adverse impacts. The soil strategic issue is its function as a soil organic carbon (SOC) stock, related to global climate change. Increased concentrations of GHG have made SOC stocks of particular concern. In this context, the type of soil becomes an interesting discussion material for studying its basic characteristics and capabilities in storing SOC. KLHK(2016) classified the land into 8 orders, with each emission factor (EF): Alfisol (FE = 1.93), Andisols (1.02), Entisols (1.2), Histosol (2.39), Incepticols (1.13), Oxisols (0.29),

Ultisols (0.29) and Vertisol (1.06). The order of histosol (peat) is categorized as the highest emission factor, whereas Oxisols and Ultisols are among the lowest. Entisols, Andisols, Alfisols and Inceptisols included young soils of volcanic material (Kurniawan et al., 2010).

The potential for greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions may originate from soil itself. Soils without fertilization or irrigation treatment, naturally, emit $\text{CH}_4 < 1 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{hour}^{-1}$ while the addition of organic or nitrogen fertilizer will increase CH_4 emissions around $1\text{-}6 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{hour}^{-1}$ (Khalil et al., 2008). The emission was influenced by the specific soil conditions, especially the temperature, which will quantify how much carbon was absorbed and released (Suntoro, Mujiyo, & Syamsiyah, 2013; Tang et al., 2017). The combination of high temperatures and low humidity had potential to release higher GHGs, as opposed to the opposite provision. CO_2 , CH_4 and N_2O gases resulting from soil carbon decomposition will contribute to the concentration of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere. At this point, information on the potential GHG emissions from agricultural land becomes important knowledge for environmental impacts. At the same time, the soil binds carbon and releases it back into atmosphere. Carbon stocks (organic and inorganic) were strongly influenced by soil types, related to soil ability to bind and store carbon (Srinivasarao et al., 2016). Environmental factors such as soil moisture, temperature (Grutzmacher et al., 2018; Srinivasarao et al., 2016), biomass burning, soil treatment technology, plant species (Khalil et al., 2008) or surface water contribute to carbon precipitation. Soil moisture and temperature were major factors in nutrient cycles and carbon stocks. Thus, each type of soil has different abilities at specific locations (Olson, Al-Kaisi, Lal, & Lowery, 2014). The Order of Vertisols, Inceptisols and Alfisols possesses mastering capability in storing SOC, while Ardisols was well storing inorganic carbon, at $< 30\text{cm}$ thickness (Bhattacharyya et al., 2009).

The rain-fed Alfisols, seeded by nuts, has higher potential emissions compared to Inceptisols (Suntoro, Mujiyo, & Syamsiyah, 2013), caused Alfisol (300 m asl) was lower than Inceptisol (1188 m asl). Another factor that affects emission levels is above ground vegetation. N concentrations in nuts (Suntoro et al., 2013) was higher than paddy (Bobihoe, 2004) or vegetables (Purba, Ashar, & Santi, 2012). CO_2 and CH_4 emissions from Andisols and Inceptisol may occur under aerobic and anaerobic conditions (Khalil et al., 2008; Tang et al., 2017). Aerobic observation (CO_2) was conducted in the post-harvest season and anaerobic conditions ($\text{CO}_2 + \text{CH}_4$) was carried out at rotation age. There was a fundamental difference between post-harvest emissions and crop rotation, in which SOC were fermented to CH_4 (Khalil et al., 2008; Tang et al., 2017) and N_2O (Khalil et al., 2008; Qi, Niu, Zhou, Jia, & Gao, 2018) during the plant growth period. Total potential of aerobic soil emissions of Andisols was in the range of

72.2-1018.6 mgC .kg⁻¹, whereas Inceptisols has the potential to release CO₂ as much as 64.9-599.8 mgC .kg⁻¹(Tang et al., 2017). The total potential of Andisols anaerobic soil emission (CO₂+ CH₄) was 124.1-184.7 mgC .kg⁻¹, whereas Inceptisols has the potential to release 69.0-248.3 mg.C .kg⁻¹(Tang et al., 2017). Under aerobic conditions with the same temperature, humidity and vegetation, Andisolhas a higher CO₂ emission potential than Inceptisols. However, at low temperature, Andisol emissions wasnot significantly different as at high temperatures (15&25 °C). The review indicated consistency with previous studies (Khalil et al., 2008; Meijide, Gruening, Goded, Seufert, & Cescatti, 2017; Qi et al., 2018; Suntoro et al., 2013), temperature has a positive relationship to SOC emissions. The temperature rise triggers the activity of soil microorganisms in decomposed soil nutrients, thus increasing in soil respiration and SOC decomposition (Meijide et al., 2017). Entisols has the potential to release GHG of 1407.4 mg .m⁻² .h⁻¹(Qi et al., 2018). Emissions of cultivated land without fertilized were lower than fertilizer or biocharamendment (Qi et al., 2018). The addition of biochar to the soil is generally to improve soil aeration and reduce emissions. However, biocharamendmentresulted in CH₄ emissions 1.6 times higher during 96 days of growth (Qi et al., 2018). Thus, the interaction between soil microorganisms and biochar increases the potential for SOC release. A contrast condition, the ability to store SOC is lower than its emission potential. The SOC potential of Alfisols between 23.28 to 49.83 Mg .ha⁻¹, Andisols of 20.10-27.36 Mg .ha⁻¹, Inceptisols 29.81-32.54 Mg ha⁻¹(Srinivasarao et al., 2016) while Entisols was 106 tons .ha⁻¹(Khanday, J.A. Wani, & Jan, 2017).

The peat land of Histosol is superior in storing SOC. The drainage and O₂ concentration was the most responsible environmental factor in decomposition process (Schulz et al., 2017). Threat to the carbon reservoir will causedimbalancing GHG concentrations in atmosphere. Emissions from peatland conversion to agriculture and grasslands contribute around 914.593 Mt.CO₂eq .year⁻¹, more than 85% from CO₂(Tubiello, Biancalani, Salvatore, Rossi, & Conchedda, 2016), while the ability to store the SOC at 390 tons .ha⁻¹(Khanday et al., 2017). The use of incentive farming systems to increase cereal productivity mostly in subtropics, Australia (De Antoni Migliorati et al., 2016). The addition of nitrogen fertilizers to Oxisols and Vertisols soils increased potential to N₂O emissionsfluks, whose risks to climate change were closed 300 times greater than that of CO₂(De Antoni Migliorati et al., 2016). Naturally, the soil releases N₂O in small concentrations. Limited water in Vertisol causes N₂O emissions to be greater than Oxisols. Vertisol has the potential to release N₂O by 0.24 ± 0.17 kgN₂O-N .ha⁻¹ compared to 0.11 ± 0.02 kgN₂O-N .ha⁻¹ in the oxysols(De Antoni Migliorati et al., 2016). The ability to absorb SOC of Oxisols,

Ultisols and Vertisol, respectively, 150 tons .ha⁻¹, 101 tons .ha⁻¹ and 38 tons .ha⁻¹ (Khanday et al., 2017).

Water Management

Water management were classified into 2 broad categories; continuously flooded and intermittently flooded (Khalil et al., 2008). Inundated condition using irrigation systems, where water flows by stages and farming systems. Natural/artificial water source areas use irrigation system, where the land is inundated in the preparation stage until the plants grow well. Flooding conditions was to reduce rice plant competition with weeds, but increase the potential for CH₄ emissions (Supriatin, 2018). The application of agrofisheery system (mina paddy) requires the land to be inundated due to agriculture and fishery responsibilities. The “mina paddy” was included in CH₄decomposition efforts on agriculture (Supriatin, 2018). Another type of unlogged land throughout the year was rainfed agriculture (Khalil et al., 2008). Rainfed agriculture land has a critical condition during the rainy season. The hard pen layer holds infiltration of rainwater, thus increasing the water level. The formation of methane gas was directly proportional to the water temperature (Supriatin, 2018). Increasedin water level will increasing the water temperature and triggering the methane. Both water management systems contribute to GHG emission.

The highest CH₄ emissions were released during rainy season, where there was an increasing water levels (Naharia, Setyanto, Arsyad, Burhan, & Aswad, 2018; Susanti, Sabiham, Anwar, & Las, 2014). Dry farm has lower emissions compared flooded and moderate land by 34% and 41% respectively (Arif et al., 2016). Supriatin (2018)stated, there were six factors for CH₄ emission in the rainy season: (1) increased water level; (2) hard pen holds water infiltration into the soil; (3) organic material by surface flow; (4) proteinas bacterial substrate; (5) anaerobic decomposition and (6) the dissolved CO₂ content of rainwater increases the amount of methanogen bacteria. CH₄ flux was influenced by water regime(Naharia et al., 2018) occurs periodically every 1-3 weeks (Arif et al., 2016). Different process in the dry season, where water level decreases compared to the rainy season. Decreasing water levels followed by an increase in O₂ concentration that triggers SOC mineralization and produces more CO₂(Susanti et al., 2014).

The intermittent irrigation has an emission risk of 2-4 times lower than that of continuously flooded (Khalil et al., 2008).

The emission of CH₄ and N₂O influenced by irrigation system. In cloudy and clay conditions, CH₄ emissions were higher (Khalil et al., 2008; Mejjide et al., 2017), whereas in intermittent conditions (Khalil et al., 2008) or post-harvesting of higher N₂O emissions (Arif et al., 2016; Mejjide et al., 2017). Intermittent

influenced by the activity of soil microorganisms through anaerobic and nitrification-denitrification process. Flooded farm lead to anaerobic activity, which results in CH₄, and N₂O emissions derived from denitrification. However, intermittent lead to increasing in rice and weeds competition (Arif et al., 2016). Increased N₂O emissions occur when the land is not inundated, permit to nitrification procedure. Ammonium in the soil converted to nitrates (Nitrosomonas bacteria), then converted to nitrites by Nitrobacter. Temporary drying in the middle of the growing season to reducing emissions of CH₄, as global warming potential (GWP) CH₄ was 25 times fold CO₂ (Tirol-padre et al., 2017). Intermittent irrigation during rice growth has been apply to reduce CH₄ emissions by 44% (Meijide et al., 2017) to 71%. CH₄ emission suppressed in a short period, during the drying. However, temperature and microorganism activity become inherent variable in CH₄ flux.

Characteristics of rice variety

Variety determines interaction agriculture with the environment, in a two-way relationship. Plants produce paddy and GHG emissions, while environment becomes carrying capacity of agricultural crops (Arif et al., 2016). Particular cultivar has the potential to release different emissions level (Meijide et al., 2017, Supriatin, 2018), thus environment can be a trigger or inhibitor of crop emission. Unthreatened Inpara 3 emission was 0.030 mg .m⁻² .day⁻¹, smaller than Inpari 30 (0.040 mg .m⁻² .day⁻¹), under the same conditions (Abduh & Annisa, 2016). Inpara 3 and Inpari 30 were tolerant cultivars in inundated land, irrigated land, swamps, basin or flood prone areas. A good root system Inpara 3 in oxidizing CH₄ believed as a superior than Inpara 30.

The lowest CH₄ emitter was Dodokan cultivar and the highest emitter was Batanghari (Supriatin, 2018). The surplus of Dodokan emissions are 1.6 grams per kg grain, while Batanghari produces emissions of 43.4 g per kg grain. Dodokan has 80-95 cm, 100-105 days of rotation period, tolerance to leaf blight (Bambang Suprihatno et al., 2010). Unlike Dodokan in irrigated land, Batanghari growing well in swampy area. Batanghari has a height of 105-112 cm, 122-128 days of growing period, intollerant from leaf blight, including Fe poisoning (Bambang Suprihatno et al., 2010). Superior productivity of Inpari 31 and Inpari 32, reciprocal with emission level, while Mekongga was lowest emission level (Kartikawati, Yulianingsih, & Wihardjaka, 2016). Biomass positively correlated with GWP, the higher productivity level sparking the higher of GWP. Crop biomass contribute to production and CH₄ transportation (Kartikawati et al., 2016).

Fertilizer decomposition

Agriculture contributed CH₄ and N₂O emission as much as 25% to climate change. Around 0-40 mg/m²/hour, ~ 170 Tg per years, in condition of farm vaporized CH₄ above this level to atmosphere compactly, even risk of N₂O 10 times fold compared CH₄ at same level (Khalil et al., 2008). Human activities believed triggering emission level through water management and manure practises. In fact, farmer have been using manure to hustle agro-productivity for a long time. Amendment organic or N-fertilizer potentially increased CH₄ or N₂O. Organic fertilizer multiply 2-4 emission of CH₄ (Meijide et al., 2017), while N-fertilizer significantly increase N₂O emission (Khalil et al., 2008; Meijide et al., 2017). Decomposition of organic fertilizer under anaerobic conditions release CH₄, excluded water level decreasing (Meijide et al., 2017). Intermittent systems can reduce CH₄ factor by 70%, both organic and N-fertilizer (Tirol-padre et al., 2017). The linear relationship between organic fertilizer-CH₄ and N fertilizer-N₂O was elementary knowledge to quantify environment hazard. Temperature play important role by mean of: (1) nutrient decomposition; (2) carbon reduction to CH₄ and (3) increasing soil respiration.

It has been mentioned above, that GHG emissions were influenced by the use of fertilizers and irrigation system. However, there was a shift pattern of agricultural management. As China, preferred using N-fertilizer and temporary flooded, a different experience from the past (Qian et al., 2014). China became top of N₂O emitter while India produce CH₄ more intent compare to other countries. Fact that disclosed by agriculture management, China implementing intensive farm while India emphasis on submerged policy. An interesting finding was that Vietnam emission greater than China even with 3 times smaller farm area. It can be pointed out that all paddy fields in Vietnam impose continuously flooded along a year (Khalil et al., 2008).

Pesticide application

Negative impacts of agro-chemicals on human health (Harsanti, Martono, & Sudibyakto, 2015), ecology (Susanti et al., 2014) and rice (Raini, 2015), got define serious concern. Human placed in the top of herbivorous making them the most vulnerable to the pesticides adverse effects. Consumption of agricultural products contaminated pesticide residues may health disruption, even death in the highest risk. Particular attention paid to the pesticides impact on human health. Risk level determined by the type and pesticides concentration, including interaction time. Harsanti et al. (2015)

reported inhibition of cholinesterase activity due to consumption of well water exposed to chlorpyrifos pesticide as much as 0.0022 ppm. The patient expressing fatigue in moderate level due to an increasing acetylcholine hydrolysis which produces choline and acetic acid. Chlorpyrifos pesticides belong to organophosphate insecticides (Harsanti et al., 2015), more slowly degraded than carbamate groups such as the phenobucarb insecticide reported by Susanti et al. (2014). Application of *paraquat dichloride herbicide*, *fenobucarb insecticide* and *difenoconazole fungicide* was proven reducing CO₂ and CH₄ emissions in tidal peatland (Susanti et al., 2014). CO₂ emissions of 19.97-28.47 mg .m⁻² .min⁻¹, lower than non-pesticide, counted for 31.28 mg .m⁻² .min⁻¹ (Susanti et al., 2014). Peatland soil organic content was responsible parameter to prevent evaporation of pesticide residu. The peatland colloidal system has a high persistence in absorbing hydrophobic pesticides (Susanti et al., 2014).

Principally, pestiside targeting agricultural pest disruction, however, interact with paddy itself. Antibiotic pesticides effectively used to reduce plant diseases caused bacteria. Antibiotic pesticides target was bacteria infected tissue. *Kasugamycin* prevent *Pyriculariaoryzae* strain growth, causing blast leaf (Kimura & Fujimoto, 2015; Raini, 2015). *Kasugamycin* was considered as friendly pesticides due to decompose by soil microbes (Raini, 2015). Similarity by *Validamycin* in different target, namely *Streptomyceshygroscopicus* (Raini, 2015; Tan, Peng, Lu, Bai, & Zhong, 2015). Another report by Bekele (2018), *Blasticin* pestiside to suppress blast, but phytotoxic to paddy and mitigate human respiratory health (Raini, 2015).

STRATEGY AND POLICY APPROACH

Agriculturemultieticipally: biomass production, income sources and environmental effect to be consider in policy decision. Synergy of the three, in practise, difficult to establish due to contradictive among other. For example, increasing productivity by intensification triggering degradation and increasing GHG emissions, or reverse interactions. At least there were 4 strategic approaches related to environmental impacts: (1) sustainable productivity (2) research investment; (3) environmentally friendly technology and (4) agroforestry.

Sustainable agriculture management

Soil ability defined by SOCsequestration (Bhattacharyya et al., 2009; Khanday et al., 2017; Srinivasarao et al., 2016) and SOC decomposition (De Antoni Migliorati et al., 2016; Fungo et al., 2017; Qi et al., 2018; Suntoro et al., 2013; Tang et al., 2017; Tubiello et al., 2016) in variety. Thus, soil fundamental function play important role to ensure sustainable agriculture management. Soil

properties become guidance for fertilization, water management, cultivar selection and pesticide application. Through Government Regulation of 150 Year 2000 and the Minister of the Environment Regulation (No. 7 Year 2006), the Government sets criteria for soil degradation to produce biomass, which degradation defined as a soil response to human activities. The critical land threshold is more strictly enforced if the area too prone to soil damage. Furthermore, the Ministry of Environment issued a classification of land capabilities, including: soil properties (physical-chemical), topography, drainage and other environmental conditions. The procedure is stipulated in the Environment Minister Regulation Number 17 Year 2009 on Guidelines for Determination of Environmental Support Capacity in Spatial Planning.

Land property placed dynamic law by human activities. Preventive attempt to be taken to inhibit soil degradation caused by human behavior, such as planting cover vegetation. There were some plant recommended as a cover vegetation by the Research, Development and Innovation Agency, Ministry of Environment and Forestry. *Centrosema pubescens* Benth., *Colopogonium mucunoides* Desv., *Crotalaria juncea* L. or *Pueraria phaseoloides* Roxb. may used to restrain erosion impacts, increase soil biomass, increase nutrients and simultaneously increase soil productivity. Another alternative pursued through water resources management, not instant due to distinction productivity wetland and dryland. Law No. 7 of 2004 interpret water resources by surface water, groundwater, rainwater and sea water on land. However, the regulation focuses more on building physical installations (irrigation networks) regardless of environment issues, in this case forest cover. Forest serves water resources including agriculture in term of increasing productivity. Thus protected forest play an important role in this context (Damiati, Lumangkun, & Dirhamsyah, 2015). However inundated farm emit more GHG against dry/temporary dry land (Arif et al., 2016; Khalil et al., 2008; Mejjide et al., 2017; Naharia et al., 2018; Supriatin, 2018; Susanti et al., 2014; Tirol-padre et al., 2017). Previous researcher recommended intermittent systems (Khalil et al., 2008; Mejjide et al., 2017; Naharia et al., 2018) to reduce emissions by 2-4 times fold lower (Khalil et al., 2008), equivalent 44% (Mejjide et al., 2017) to 71% (Tirol-padre et al., 2017) reduction of CH₄ emissions.

Extensification is the last strategy to boasting agro-productivity, synergized with intensification. Principle reasoning originated from soil property and the ability to store SOC. Critical or unproductive forest turn in into agriculture land, expected to increase C-soil stock. Printing paddy land originated from forest was regulated by Minister of Environment and Forestry Decree No. 180 Year 2017 concerning Indicative Maps of Forest Area Allocation for Provision of Land Resources Object of Agrarian Reform (TORA). In general,

TORA allocation were divided into 7 criteria, in which agricultural sector gets 1.29 million ha (26.61%) of TORA. Redistribution of assets was arranged by Law 56/PRP Year 1960, where agricultural land was limited to between 5-20 hectares per person or families. The other side of extensification was SF by maintaining principal forest function (Decree of the Minister of Environment and Forestry No.22 of 2017).

Table 2. Distribution of TORA by land use

TORA			Social Forestry (SF)		
No	Criteria	(ha)	No	Criteria	Million ha
1	Plantation (20%)	437,937	1	Production forest	5.938
2	Converted production forest	2,169,960	2	Protected forest	3.167
3	Printing new farm	65,363	3	Peatland	2.222
4	Transmigration settlement	514,909	4	Concession	2.134
5	Settlement	439,116			
6	Cultivated (paddy & fishpond)	379,227			
7	Cultivated farm (dryland)	847,038			
Total		4,853,550	Total		13.462

Rice varieties development

Plant breeding through improved variety characteristic intended to increase productivity, the number and index per ha. The harvest potential closely related to number of productive tillers, number of grains per panicle, percentage of grain, and rice weight (Abdullah, Tjokrowidjojo, & Sularjo, 2008). Paddy variety showed similarity characteristic index and distincting traits (Sitaresmi, Wening, Rakhmi, Yunani, & Susanto, 2013). Amylopectin and amylose determine rice texture, the lower amylose level-more fluffy (Rohaeni, Sinaga, & Ishaq, 2012). Local varieties have been bred and transform to superior characteristics, in terms of growth and yield potential. The varieties number till 2018 reached 100, including new variety: 6 Inpari variety, 4 Inpago and 2 Inpara (Moh. Ismail Wahab et al., 2017).

Table 3. New paddy variety by characteristic (Moh. Ismail Wahab et al., 2017)

Variety	HAS	High (cm)	WPS (gr)	Amilosa (%)	AR (t ha ⁻¹)	Note
InpariTarabas	131	122	26.4	17.73	4.10	Sawah, lokal
InpariMunawacitaAgritan	123	122	28.77	19.17	6.03	Sawah
InpariMustabanAgritan	118	105	27.17	13.13	6.59	Sawah
InpariSiliwangiAgritan	111	111	26.4	21.2	7.4	Sawah
InpariPadjadjaranAgritan	105	97	26	20.6	7.8	Sawah
InpariCakrabuanaAgritan	104	105	27.1	22	7.5	Sawah
InpagoRindang 1 Agritan	113	130	27.6	26.4	4.62	Gogo
InpagoRindang 1 Agritan	113	138	31.3	16.4	4.2	Gogo
InpagoLuhur 1	124	120	26.4	21	4.8	Gogo
InpagoLuhur 2	123	110	24.6	24.3	4.6	Gogo
Inpara 10 BLB	126	101	-	24.9	5.0	Rawa
InparaPurwa	121	105	-	3.8	4.9	Rawa

Note: HAS = harvest days after seedling; WPS = weight per thousand seed; AR = average yield

Specifically, the finding for research-based paddy varieties was regulated by Minister of Agriculture Regulation No. 61 of 2011 concerning Testing, Assessment, Release and Withdrawal of Varieties. This regulation intended to provide protection and benefits assurance of research-based new varieties that do not harm farmer and environment. At least, there are 2 input for: the environmental impact and the local varieties test time. Agricultural practises impact to environment needs serious attention, related GHG emissions. Crop varieties (Abduh & Annisa, 2016; Kartikawati et al., 2016; Supriatin, 2018), soil (De Antoni Migliorati et al., 2016; Fungo et al., 2017; Qi et al., 2018; Suntoro et al., 2013; Tang et al., 2017; Tubiello et al., 2016) and water management (Arif et al., 2016; Khalil et al., 2008; Meijide et al., 2017; Naharia et al., 2018; Supriatin, 2018; Susanti et al., 2014; Tirol-padre et al., 2017) released different emission level. Thus, emission level needs to be explicitly regulated in this regulation. It is deemed not to change regulation substance due in article 26, environmental aspects have been accommodated as a team member of assessors to evaluate new variety. The second input, reduction of local varieties test time prior to release as superior varieties. It was mentioned article 17 that category of superior local varieties if "has been cultivated more than 5 (five) years for seasonal crops or 5 (five) years of harvest for annual crops". The test time is considered too long for local varieties. At least, there are 2 backgrounds: local variety have been adapted well to domestic environment and climate change dynamic. Indonesia was secondary center of origin of the rice species (Sitaresmi et al., 2013), thus it have been tolerance to the domestic environment. In fact, rice have been a staple cultivated for generations.

Environmentally friendly technology (Emission management).

The 2013-2016 FAO statistics showed that agriculture sector in Indonesia emits 165,175.73 Gg CO₂eq. Year-1, increment of 1-3% per year. Rice cultivation contribute as much as 38.5%, was highest, and followed by cultivation in organic soil 21.4%. While enteric fermentation and synthetic fertilizer contributed 11%, respectively. Government issued Presidential Regulation Number 61 of 2011 concerning the National Action Plan for Reducing Greenhouse Gas Emissions (RAN-GRK), and agriculture being a special discussion (*Table 4*). Emission reduction target was 0.008 Gt CO₂e (scenario 26%) or 0.011 Gt CO₂e (scenario 41%). The first based on Government efforts itself, the second with international assistance. Referring to FAO data and Presidential Regulation, agricultural cultivation and organic land cultivation are the main priorities, followed by enteric fermentation and fertilizers / pesticides. At this point, the authors will focusing more on land and fertilizer regime.

Table 4. Emission reduction target by agricultural practices(Presidential Regulation of 61 Year 2016)

No	Practices	Million ton CO ₂ eq
1	Repair and maintenance of irrigation Improved 1.34 million ha of irrigation networks Operationalization and maintenance of irrigation networks 2.32 million ha	0.16
2	Optimizing land Management of agricultural land-non fired 300,500 ha	4.81
3	Cultivation technology Environmentally friendly technology covering 2.03 million ha	32.42
4	Fertilizers and biopesticides Using of fertilizer and biopesticide 250,000 ha	10.0
5	Other land use Oil palm 860,000 ha Rubber 105,200 ha Cacao 687,000 ha	74.53 2.38 5.42
6	Agricultural energy resources Waste utilization (1,500 group)	1.01
	Total	130.73

Various threat cause soil to degrade. Undertaking to prevent degradation was biochar amendment(Augustenberg et al., 2012; Pari, Roliadi, & Komarayati, 2013; Qian et al., 2014). Biochar (C) was a pyrolysis product of various urban organic waste (Qian et al., 2014)biomass especially ligno-cellulose containing materials (Augustenberg et al., 2012; Pari et al., 2013), containing C/N high ratio (Van Zwieten et al., 2015), 400-800 °C (Pari et al., 2013). Other element present uncontested in ligno-cellulose material such as:H, O, S, P and inorganic

content. Further development of carbonization techniques produces byproduct and derivative product, ordinary called integrated biochar or 3 in 1 product (Gusmailina, Komarayati, & Pari, 2016; Sri Komarayati, Gusmailina, & Pari, 2011, 2013; Pari, 2014; Pari et al., 2013). The by-products of carbonization was liquid smoke and derivative products into bioactive biochar composites. Carbonylation yields generally 75-80% in range, other parts including volatile groups turn into liquid smoke by condensation process (Pari et al., 2013). Biochar, with its pore, can hold soil water (Karhu, Mattila, Bergström, & Regina, 2011) saturate SOC (Liu et al., 2018) and nutrients uptake (Liu et al., 2018; Werner et al., 2018). Biochar or the three, are believed to be soil improvement agents, while increasing SOC uptake. Thus, carbonization technology was relevant to the implementation of Presidential Regulation 61 Year 2011, in frame of reducing GHG emissions, in addition to energy source (Pari, 2014). Simple technology but useful, produced by utilizing biomass waste (Pari, 2014). Biochar production mechanism may carried out through traditional kiln, modified drum kiln, semi-continuous kiln(Pari et al., 2013).

Biochar positive effects through fertility increment (Augustenborg et al., 2012; Sri Komarayati et al., 2013; Liu et al., 2018; Qian et al., 2014; Werner et al., 2018), pH regulation (Liu et al., 2018; Qian et al., 2014; Sandiwantoro, Eko, & Islami, 2017; Yuriyah, Nurani, Utami, & Silitonga, 2016), aeration (Karhu et al., 2011; Van Zwieten et al., 2015), habitat of microorganisms (Sri Komarayati et al., 2013; Van Zwieten et al., 2015; Zheng, Wang, Luo, Wang, & Xing, 2018), water holding capacity (Karhu et al., 2011) and reducing emissions (Augustenborg et al., 2012; Grutmacher et al., 2018; Karhu et al., 2011; Pari, 2014; Van Zwieten et al., 2015). Specifically for water holding and aeration, creating anaerobic conditions and denitrification, attempt must be taken as long as air was not used by plant respiration (Van Zwieten et al., 2015). Beneficiary of biochar and compost while preparing a macro nutritional. Sri Komarayati et al., (2013)result showed that C and K concentrations had a significant, but there was a gradual downward trend in N and P. Increases in N and P only occurred in biochar amendment of 20% (Sri Komarayati et al., 2013). This fact was similar with previous studies (Karhu et al., 2011; Qian et al., 2014), an N₂O increase emissions occurs while compost mineralization, after then decreased. Biochar augment has been proven to improve soil fertility, increasing agricultural yields. Qian et al. (2014)reported an increase of 28.1% and 31.4% with peanut leather based biochar and urban waste.

Agriculture recognized to be an attractive discussion due to contradictive among food security and environmental impact. Food sources proscuted by population demand, in other hand, environmental impact was an obligation. Biochar amendment believed to be midpoint between the two. CH₄

absorbed in biochar pore, reducing emission level, and preserve 96% compared to unthreatment from 49.6 to 97.4 g CH₄-C .ha⁻¹(Karhu et al., 2011). CH₄ uptake caused by soil aeration and CH₄ diffusion (Karhu et al., 2011). Different levels of decline reported in rice fields around the Yangtze River, CH₄ emissions decreased by more than 45%(Qian et al., 2014). Similar interaction in decreasing CH₄, biochar amendment suppress N₂O emissions. Biochar availability alleviate substrate as nitrification-denitrification mechanism. Gross N-mineralization exceed 269%, compared to without biochar treatment (Case et al., 2015). Biochar produced based woody or agricultural residues, has a significant impact on reducing N₂O emissions, compared to other material (Van Zwieten et al., 2015). Miscanthus based biochar has been proven reduce emissions level of 91-95% N₂O in indigent organic soils and 56-61% in high organic soils (Augustenborg et al., 2012). Even in sandy loam occured similar respond, biochar addition recorded a 91% N₂O reduction (Case et al., 2015). Lowering N₂O emissions in irrigated rice fields was reported fetch 40% (Qian et al., 2014). It was concluded, that biochar pathway function mechanism, emission inhibitor, to soil through soil property improvement (physical, chemical, biological) and the interaction of all three.

Agroforestry system

A mosaic between agriculture and forestry lies in the agroforestry system. Traditionally, the mechanism has been implemented in various countries followed debate on continuing economic deflating. In environmental side, the consideration based on emission factor. Harmonious inter-connection between agriculture and environment believed to intensify carbon uptake (De Stefano & Jacobson, 2018; Dhaliwal, Kukal, & Sharma, 2018; Geelani, Qaiser, Khan, Mughal, & Husain, 2018) by 15 time fold compared agriculture-agriculture combination or 30 more in vegetable-vegetable combination (Geelani et al., 2018). Agroforestry let trees confer additional biomass, either above or below the ground. Forest plant and root systems become carbon holder when harvesting agricultural crops. SOC dynamics during transition period: forestry-agroforestry reduce SOC by 24-26%, while agriculture-agroforestry causes a significant increase by 24-40% (De Stefano & Jacobson, 2018). However, carbon stocks apply to certain condition, influenced by structure, aging, functional components and intensity of management (Geelani et al., 2018; Masripatin, Pari, et al., 2010). Table 5shows the structure of plants and aging affecting SOC in Indonesia agroforestry.

Table 5. Carbon stock of agroforestry system in Indonesia

No	Agroforestry system	Year	ton C .ha-1
1.	Cofeemulty-strata in Lampung		
	Timber based	20	39.7
	Fruit based	20	42.2
	Shade based	20	48.5
2	<i>Agroforestry di Tasikmalaya</i>		
	Sengon	2-6	25.15
	Senngon, mahoni, manglid	2-6	19.51
	Sengon, afrika, cengkeh, dan tisuk	2-10	25.30
	Sengon, avocado, kidamar	2-10	23.21
3	<i>Agroforestry di Ciamis</i>		
	Afrika, Mahoni, Durian	2-10	48.68
	Sengon, Afrika, Cengkeh, Parkia, Mahoni	2-10	85.27
	Kiteja, mahoni, sengon	2-10	49.76
	Sengon, mahoni, afrika, tangkil	2-10	41.61
4	<i>Agroforestry cinnamon</i>		
	Cinnamon dan kentang	12	22.7
5	<i>Repong Damar</i>		
	Traditional damar	40-60	102.7
	Intensive damar	40-60	102.7

RECYCLING BIOMASS TO PREVENT ENVIRONMENT POLLUTION

Agricultural residu and household waste may converted to biochar(López-Cano et al., 2018). Agricultural wastes such as wheat straw (Taherymoosavi, Joseph, Pace, & Munroe, 2018), corncob (Zhao, Xue, Long, & Hu, 2018), peanut shell (Zhao et al., 2018), cotton stalks (Zhao et al., 2018), rice straw (Liu et al., 2018; Werner et al., 2018; Yang et al., 2018), barley (Jazini, Soleimani, & Mirghaffari, 2017; Kang et al., 2018) as material for biochar production (*Table 6*). With all its advantages, biochar was suspected to be a good addition to soil (Taherymoosavi et al., 2018).

Taherymoosavi et al. (2018) reported biochar characteristics using wheat straw (Ws) and wheat straw-basal soil (WsBs). Relative mass loss of Wswas higher than WsBs, the effect of high non-volatile minerals on basal soils (Taherymoosavi et al., 2018). Mineral concentration at temperatures of 450 °C and 650 °C, most of them have similar mineral content at 550 °C. Al, Fe, Ca, Na, Mg at WsBs 550°C, was higher than other materials, except K was lower than Ws550 °C (Taherymoosavi et al., 2018). Wsbiochar, as expected, have a fixed carbon, moisture and volatile material significantly higher than WsBs, except for ash content (Taherymoosavi et al., 2018). The ash content has an opposite relation to fixed-C, the lower ash content-the higher the fixed carbon content. In contrast to the relationship of ash content-fixed-C, the pyrolysis temp against

fixed-C (Taherymoosavi et al., 2018) and temperature-pH, have a positive relationship. Fixed-C benefiting soil carbon sequestration (Taherymoosavi et al., 2018), came from the stability ratio of C, H and O on biochar, H/C and O/C below 0.2, a stable crystal graphite (Chia et al., 2014).

Biochar production using corncob, peanut shell and cotton stalks was carried out by (Zhao et al., 2018). C-content in each material contain of 68-84%, H and N respectively, 2.4-5.5% & 0.2-1.8% (Zhao et al., 2018). The dynamics of C, H and N can be observed at temperature treatment. The trend of C flux tends to increase in all material and temperature, except corncob which has a decrease at 600 °C, while H and N tend to rise at 450°C and then decrease at of 600 °C (Zhao et al., 2018). Biochar combination of rice straw and swine manure shows different characteristics with other. Swine manure shows affected of biochar increasing yield and dust content (Meng, Tao, Wang, Liu, & Xu, 2018) caused decrease manure mineral. The highest C was rice straw biochar and decreasing along addition of swine manure. Conversion barley into biochar with difference procedure: temperature treatment of 0, 300, 400, 500 °C (Jazini et al., 2017) and at a single temperature of 400 °C (Kang et al., 2018). Jazini et al. (2017) shows detail dynamics of element and molar ration, physico-chemical with temperature fluks. Along with the pyrolysis temperature there were increasing on ash content, C, and N; where volatile, O, H, O/C and H/C tend to fall; while S was fluctuatively (Jazini et al., 2017). The benefit of C, H, N, S and H/C content belong to Kang et al. (2018), while O and O/C benefit belong to (Jazini et al., 2017). Uncontested, material initial threatment gives the advantages of C, H, N, and S in the product. Drying treatment at 70 °C (oven) for 2 days gave C (71.5%), H (4.7%), N (1.3%) and S (0.2%) to 56.99%, 2.05%, 0.87% and 0.14%. The characteristics is important, closely related to SOC residence time, soil pores and holding water capacity.

Table 6. Characteristics of agricultural residue biochar

Parameter	Wheat straw	Corncob	Peanutshell	Cotton stalks	Rice Straw	Jelai
Proximate						
Moisture, %	1.6-3.9 a	-	-	-	-	-
Ash, %	20.8-81.9 a	-	-	-	28.00-47.00 c	8.1-12.2 d
Volatile, %	3.4-15.2 a	-	-	-	-	21.7-52.9 d
Fixed carbon, %	13.4-65.1 a	-	-	-	-	-
Ultimate						
C, %	81.0-90.4 a	75.91-81.80 b	69.27-82.44 b	68.11-84.19 b	36.34-54.98 c	43.13-66.46 d
	-	-	-	-	-	71.5 e
H, %	3.0-4.4 a	3.631-4.013 b	2.401-5.065 b	2.842-5.554 b	1.95-2.60 c	1.44-6.27 d
	-	-	-	-	-	4.7 e
N, %	0.9-1.6 a	0.285-0.599 b	1.425-1.896 b	0.832-1.135 b	1.5-2.08 c	0.48-0.87 d
	-	-	-	-	-	1.3 e

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Parameter	Wheat straw	Corn cob	Peanut shell	Cotton stalks	Rice Straw	Jelai
S, %	0.1-0.3 a	-	-	-	-	0.13-0.14 d
	-	-	-	-	-	0.2 e
O, %	5.7-13.5 a	-	-	-	10.86-15.00 c	19.08-42.01 d
	-	-	-	-	-	22.3 e
H/C	0.033-0.054 a	-	-	-	0.05 c	0.04-0.15 d
	-	-	-	-	-	0.79 e
O/C	0.097-0.166 a	-	-	-	-	0.29-0.97 d
	-	-	-	-	-	0.23 e

Note: a=Taherymoosavi et al. (2018): wheat straw & wheat straw-basal, t= 450 °C, 550 °C, 650 °C; b= Zhao et al. (2018): t= 300 °C, 450 °C, 600 °C; c= Meng et al. (2018): t=400 °C, ratio rice straw (R) :swine manure (M)= R, R3M1, R1M1, R1M3, M; d= Jazini et al. (2017): barley straw, t=300 °C, 400 °C, 500 °C; e= Kang et al. (2018): barley straw, t= 400 °C

However, there is no single empirical data due to commodities variation and different in harvesting techniques. The entity approach to amount of harvest per year, as an example, combined agricultural and plantation sectors produce more than 132 million tons of biomass, while forestry alone produced more than 41 million m³ of raw material. The three were transformed into a biomass bank as biochar materials

Table 7. Biomass bank in the farm-plantation and forestry sectors

Comodity	Production in ton			Unit
	2013	2014	2015	
Paddy	71,279,709	70,846,465	75,397,841	ton
Corn	18,511,853	19,008,426	19,612,435	ton
Soybean	779,992	954,997	963,183	ton
Bean	906,350	883,485	876,912	ton
Palm oil	27,782,000	29,278,200	31,070,000	ton
Coconut	3,051,600	3,005,900	2,920,700	ton
Coffe bean	675,900	643,900	639,400	ton
Cocoa	720,900	728,400	593,300	ton
Natural forest	45,770,454	44,963,519	35,290,288	m ³
Consession	4,852,881	5,447,041	5,879,380	m ³

Source: (Central Bureau of Statistics, processed)

Biochar has advantages as a soil amendment: increasing nutrient uptake (S. Komarayati & Pari, 2012; Suwardji, Utomo, & Sukartono, 2012; Werner et al., 2018), increasing yields (Sandiwantoro et al., 2017; Werner et al., 2018), binding to soft metal Cd (Liu et al., 2018), soil aggregation (Suwardji et al., 2012; Zheng et al., 2018), reducing emissions (Grutmacher et al., 2018). Soil nutrients are important for plant growth and productivity, but are often lost due to degradation or washed away by surface runoff. Biochar amendment believed to be able to withstand these effect. Biochar present immobilize P, K, and Mg, and

feeds to plants, especially P as a growth agent (Farrar et al., 2018; Liu et al., 2018; López-Cano et al., 2018; Werner et al., 2018), except for N there was an interim downward trend (Liu et al., 2018; W, Kusnarta, & Sukartono, 2018; Werner et al., 2018). Biochar can also be used as a soil metal binder. The addition of biochar, with the ability of cation exchange capacity (CEC) and pH regulation (Ohsowski, Dunfield, Klironomos, & Hart, 2018; Zheng et al., 2018), capture Cd through cation deposition and CEC (Liu et al., 2018). This type of cation exchange also helps in binding to soil minerals (Ohsowski et al., 2018; Zheng et al., 2018), thereby increasing the aggregation process (Zheng et al., 2018).

Cd exchange has an internal relationship with SOC, negatively, the higher the Cd content will decrease SOC. Rice husk biochar was superior in absorbing Cd than bamboo biochar (Liu et al., 2018). The wider pore surface on biochar gives more opportunities to absorb Cd metal, than absorbed by plants. Another benefit is through reducing the level of agricultural land emissions. The pyrolysis process causes the C-chain to be more stable, converting C to an aromatic ring (Grutmacher et al., 2018; Yang et al., 2018), more resistant to abiotic and biotic decomposition (Grutmacher et al., 2018). Therefore, it increases retention of C in the soil. C-residence time in soil was 3 times fold longer and 7 times lower in terms of emissions, biochar compare to manure (Grutmacher et al., 2018). Charcoal amelioration in sandy soils has increased cumulative CO₂ in the soil, compared to sandy loam soils (El-Naggar et al., 2018).

Furthermore, biochar increased plant growth, root dry mass and shoot were 4.6-10.7% higher than without biochar, depending on biochar material (López-Cano et al., 2018). A higher increase in red chili, a combination of biochar and manure increases the fruit mass by 19% (W et al., 2018). Biochar residue reported to provide high growth stimulants, leaves number and mass of soybeans (Yuriyah et al., 2016). An increasing in sweet corn yield of 24.6% through biochar treatment 12 t ha⁻¹ (Sandiwantoro et al., 2017). Another fact, the peanut dry weight of increased by more than 84% in biochar treatment 7 t ha⁻¹, excepted high and the leaves number per plant (Suparta, Kartini, & Situmeang, 2018). Other findings, the addition of biochar increases ginger harvest (Farrar et al., 2018). Similar to agricultural crops, forest crop responses to biochar show positive interactions. Sawdust biochar amendment were 5-10%, provides high growth stimulants 16-33 times fold in Jabon and more than 2-6 times in sengon tillers (Komarayati & Pari, 2012). Application biochar and compost in agroforestry system, the yield of agriculture plantation like broccoly and pokcoy increase 2-4 times under *Pinus merkusii* plantation

CONCLUSIONS

The implementation of agricultural land intensification and extensification causes a contradictory impact. Food resources is a population demand, the other hand, negative impacts on the environment need to be taken into account. Agricultural practices, with various modifications, are believed to increase national food security. However, super-strict supervision needs to be implemented to control its interaction with the environment. Farming Activities: (1) land management; (2) cultivars; (3) irrigation scheme; (4) fertilization and (5) pests eradication, in a single process has potential to reduce environmental quality. Periodic analysis needs to maintain harmonious interaction between agriculture and the environment. Further more, Government policy is absolute to support sustainable agricultural practices. Agricultural practices for using low emission cultivars, intermittent irrigation, agroforestry practices and biochar applications are recommended to support sustainable agriculture management and to minimize environment impacts. Application biochar, compost and liquid smoke (3 in 1 technology) from agriculture and forest residue in agroforestry system its can be reduce CH₄, N₂O and CO₂ emission gas and increasing the yield of agriculture.

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